

A 2-year retrospective into the open information landscape: Learnings from the TOBI project

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Abstract

The poster presents an overview of the diverse outcomes of the project Towards Open Bibliometric Indicators (TOBI), ran by the ETH Library (ETH Zurich). The project was launched in March 2023 with the goal of assessing the usability of open scholarly metadata for bibliometric analyses in Switzerland.

The poster discusses main project findings grouped into three categories:

(1) Bibliometric analyses of viability and data quality of selected open scholarly metadata databases, with a special focus on Swiss higher educational institutions (HEIs). On the poster we present three such analyses. Firstly, we have undertaken a survey of the biggest and most versatile databases of scholarly metadata, comparing them with commercial databases. Secondly, focusing on Swiss HEIs, we have assessed the visibility of various research institutions in selected open and commercial bibliometric databases, highlighting coverage differences across institution sizes and types [1]. Thirdly, we have analysed the proportions of research outputs written in Swiss national languages.

(2) Development of new methods to systematically evaluate the data quality. On the poster we present a set of visuals referring to a new formal method to identify and describe interdependence between columns in a given dataset. The approach introduced fully in the article [2] allows for a more systematic approach to data cleaning.

(3) Actions undertaken to promote usage of open bibliometric data in Switzerland. On the poster we discuss various deliverables, which originated within the project and involved the scientometric community in Switzerland, such as: curation of institutional metadata in ROR and OpenOrgs; creating a set of code tutorials to empower analysts at Swiss HEIs to use open bibliometric data sources [3]; publishing a paper with 14 recommendations to enhance the visibility of research in the open research information landscape, with articles written by representatives from various Swiss research institutions [4].

Additionally, the poster presents a brief overview of major developments in the open research information landscape, such as the launch of the Barcelona Declaration, and shifts in national strategies including Switzerland's Open Science policies.

The project fits into the trend of increasing reliability and strategic value of open data in research evaluation, while highlighting how community-driven improvements and institutional engagement can enhance quality of scholarly metadata, leading to more responsible research assessment.

References

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